

Dissolution process of Bioglass 45S5 in physiological and acidic environment

A.Švančárková^{1,2}, D.Galusková¹, H. Kaňková¹, M. Michálek¹, D.Galusek¹

¹ FunGlass, Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass, Department of Biomaterials, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

(E-mail: annasvancarkova@tnuni.sk)

²Faculty of Chemical and Food Technology STU, Radlinského 9, 812 37 Bratislava, Slovakia

ABSTRACT

The 45S5 Bioglass (BG) prepared by Hench with weight composition 45% SiO₂, 24.5% CaO, 24.5 Na₂O and 6% P₂O₅ is a bioactive material that stimulates bone repair. In aqueous environment, this material undergoes a series of reactions to create a surface layer of hydroxy-apatite (HA) and hydroxy-carbonate apatite. The incorporation of ions in BG can enhance the therapeutic effects of the material.

In this study, the effect of different solution media to the corrosion behavior of 45S5 bioactive glass (BG) and 45S5 bioglass doped with boron (4 wt%) or zinc (4 wt%) was investigated. In vitro tests were carried out in simulated body fluid (pH 7.4) and acetic acid buffered with sodium acetate (pH 4) solution simulating inflammatory environment.

Glass powders with theoretical composition (in wt%) described in Tab.1. were fabricated by conventional melting. The prepared bulk glass was crushed and sieved to achieve particle size $\leq 25\mu\text{m}$

Tab.1: Comparison of the theoretical and experimental composition (ICP OES analyses of samples decomposed in mineral acids) of tested bioactive glass in wt%.

wt%	45S5		45S5+4B		45S5+4Zn	
	Theor. Comp.	Experim. comp.	Theor. Comp.	Experim.c omp.	Theor. Comp.	Experim.c omp.
SiO ₂	45	42.0±2.1*	44.5	42.9±1.9*	44.5	42.3±2.4*
P ₂ O ₅	6	6.1±1.2	5.9	8.5±2.7	5.9	9.0±3.1
CaO	24.5	23.5±2.3	21.4	21.7±1.5	21.4	21.7±1.0
Na ₂ O	24.5	23.4±1.8	24.2	23.1±0.8	24.2	23.3±2.1
ZnO	-	-	-	-	4	3.7±0.8
B ₂ O ₅	-	-	4	3.9±0.6	-	-

*normalized to 100%

Dissolution studies were performed at the static conditions in the neutral and acidic environment.

The 35 mg of glass powder was immersed in 25 ml of solution at 37°C for 1, 2, 4, 8 and 24 hours. After each time period, composition of corrosion solutions were analyzed using inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometer (ICP-OES, Agilent 5100). Each experiment was performed in three parallels. The amount of released ions (in mg/L) were presented as normalized leached values of the respective element -NL_i (in mg of element/g of

element in initial powder).

NL values were calculated based using the following (1):

$$NL_i = \frac{c_i * V}{w_i * m_s}, \quad (1)$$

where V is volume of corrosion medium, w_i - mass fraction of an element in the sample, c_i - concentration of an element i in the sample and m_s is weight of the initial powder.

In SBF solution, silicon concentration increased in all materials rapidly during the first 1-2 h (Fig.1). This initial faster release of Si occurs during the second stage of the deposition of HA layer on the surface of BG. During this second stage Si–O–Si bonds are broken and soluble silica is released to the solution. The reason for decrease of phosphorus in solution is the strong adsorption of phosphorus ions from SBF solution to the glass surface. Adsorption of phosphorus ions from SBF is due to solution supersaturation necessary to form Ca–P rich reaction layer (the fourth stage of the deposition of HA layer). For samples 45S5+Zn and 45S5+B we did not observe any significant decrease of phosphorus content in corrosion solutions. The reason can be higher content of phosphorus in this untreated samples (Tab.1), also it is not necessary to pump so much ions of phosphorus for creating HA layer from the SBF. In SBF, elution of ions was the slowest in 45S5+Zn. In this material, the release of zinc as a potential antibacterial inhibitor was meeting the limit of quantification.

Fig.1: Time dependence of the ions released from the studied glass systems into SBF of 45S5, 45S5+4Zn and 45S5+B.

In HAc/NaAc buffer, all tested bioglasses showed fast release of ions (Fig.2). While the silicate network was relatively stable in acidic environment, and release of Si was relatively slow, the network modifiers Na, Ca, P and Zn or B leached out from the material very quickly. This behaviour is potentially favorable for curing or stopping inflammation process in the body through rapid dissolution of bioactive glass and release of zinc to fight bacterial infection. Incorporation of zinc in the glass structure increases its network connectivity [1]. However when zinc is leached out in acidic environment already in the early stage of the dissolution process, the residual glass tends to dissolve rapidly

Fig.2: Time dependence of the ions released from the studied glass systems in acetic acid/sodium acetate buffer (pH4) of 45S5, 45S5+4Zn and 45S5+B.

Keywords: bioactive glass, dissolution, acetic acid/sodium acetate buffer, simulated body fluid

LITERATURE

[1] Blochberger, M., Hupa, L., Brauer, D.S. Influence of zinc and magnesium substitution on ion release from Bioglass 45S5 at physiological and acidic pH, *Biomed.Glasses* 1 (2015) 93-107.

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